

LEARNING TOGETHER EACH OTHER'S LANGUAGE

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Abstract. *The author presents the language learning technique through his life experiences in this thesis. He also explains his reasons for learning world languages : English, Spanish, French, and Uzbek.*

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Since officially September this year, I have lived here in Tashkent. My wife is Uzbek, and we live with her mom and our cat, Miya, in a neighborhood considered part of the center. I have taught French at the Alliance Française since last Spring and have worked at Profi University since mid-October as Deputy Head of the Tourism Department. Behind this bombastic title, my occupation consists of acting as an Academic Coordinator to ensure that the double degree program we are developing with a French higher school of tourism is compliant with our mutual commitments and the regulations to which we are subject, as well as to advice and accompany students regarding the exchange year some of them will accomplish in their fourth academic year.

Before September, I had come several times to Uzbekistan. The first was a week ago, in November 2018, in Buxoro – Samarqand – Toshkent. I was invited to have a plov at a local family's through an online accommodation platform. At the end of the dinner, I was warmly invited to return to your country, which I did a few months later, in April 2019. The daughter of the house and I confessed our mutual feelings. However, it was not before last year that I returned to Uzbekistan, and we married only this year, in Spring. The pandemic has passed by, and so have episodes of our complicated lives. Adversity on a global and personal scale made us stronger and made our love grow. Moreover, we are now married and living together here after all we have been through. As a binational and bicultural couple, it is, if not natural, logical that we start learning each other's language.

It would be fairer if my wife were here this morning to tell you this story instead of me since she is much more gifted in languages than I am. As she has family obligations and trusts me to tell you about our mutual apprenticeship, I will do my best. Above all, we come from different linguistic backgrounds. She is Uzbek. She was born at the very end of the Soviet Union, but the primary language spoken at the family table was Russian. Uzbek is her mother language, but she knows Russian even better. Since her mother is an English teacher, my wife also has excellent proficiency in this language, which we mostly use to communicate. I am French, and though I have lived in seven countries before coming here, I can only speak, besides my mother language, a passable English and a slightly more convincing Italian, with a proficiency in the latter two languages equal to a C1 level. My wife's English, as her mother's and as the English of many Uzbek speakers, is influenced by American English, while mine is more imbued with the European roots of Dusty Springfield's language.

For historical reasons dating back to the conquest by William of Normandy, English is made of 29% words of French origin (en.wikipedia.org, 2024) and an

additional 29% words of Latin or another romance language, which makes it easier for me – I studied Latin in middle school – to make it mine. It is not the case for most of my fellow citizens, whose reputation for being reluctant to speak English is well established. In 2023, French people were the 43rd in the world in terms of English proficiency (en.wikipedia.org, 2024), on a par with Cuba, and well behind Benelux, Nordics, German-speaking, Baltic countries, but also Croatia, Greece, Poland, Bulgaria, Hungary, Slovakia, Serbia, Czechia, Moldova, Albania, and all the European romance language countries, namely Portugal, Romania, Italy and Spain. Are we that bad at English and foreign languages? Or are we just reluctant to speak the nowadays uncontested *lingua franca mundi*, a status once ours? Could it be jealousy?

In a globalized world, knowing English is mandatory to feel like a fish in the water. So why bother learning other languages? Why did I learn Italian starting in middle school? Most French pupils have the choice between only German and Spanish as a second foreign language, but, being in a region bordering Italy, I could choose Italian. I remember I was offered to learn German, as I had good grades and German is considered difficult, attracting the best students regardless of their interest in the language and its cultures (with an "s" because, across time, Germany and Austria have developed specific and different cultures within the European civilization). Spanish? I never considered this option. Spanish came later: it is easy to read, and its rules are less tricky than French. My mother briefly lived in Rome at a young age. Her family had friends in Turin, a few hour's drive from home, and we spent a lot of Sundays there when I was a child. However, I mostly remember I insisted then on the ease of learning Italian, even saying it would save me a lot of painful working hours – I was lazy and proud of it. I was 12, and I had the right to be lazy. If later I happened to briefly regret not having learned German (after falling in love with Wien), I never regretted being lazy because Italian is easy for a French

speaker and unspeakably (and subjectively) beautiful. Its melody is reflected in the opera and the music *leggera – dalla Scala a San Remo*, and the country, with its mountains, monuments, and coasts, shows an unequaled variety of landscapes, climates, and terroirs. Italian is for my *piacere e felicità*. If English is mandatory, Italian, for me, is necessary.

My wife learned Russian, which was spoken at home, along with Uzbek. She also learned English at school and took advantage of her mother's profession as an English teacher. Since October, she has been learning French at the Alliance Française, where I teach twice weekly. I have also started learning Russian, as the Alliance Française provides its native French teachers with such courses. Why not use Uzbek, which is the country's only official language? Uzbekistan's language policy is not the topic here; I will leave it aside and keep it for another statement when I know more about this fascinating subject.

My wife is learning French at an A1 level as a beginner, twice two hours a week, with an Uzbek teacher trained to teach beginners. Being a French teacher and a native, I do not consider myself, for the moment, ready to teach beginners because it requires pedagogic skills I do not have now. This is why I rejected several offers to teach French to beginners, and I am convinced that, natively or not, teaching to beginners is severe. My Uzbek colleagues at the Alliance Française or Profi University do it much better than I would. However, when we review the lessons with my wife, with the notebook and the notes she takes, it is inspiring, and I can measure how accurate the notebook is, how good the teacher is, and how outstanding the student is.

My Russian lessons are given by a fellow Alliance Française teacher, a Uzbek woman who speaks fluent Russian and is very lovely, understanding, and patient. Unfortunately, our material is not as good as the one given to my wife and her fellow students. Moreover, my hectic professional rhythm does not always make it possible

for me to attend the lessons. So, my wife is much more advanced in French than I am in Russian, and it would be relatively more straightforward now to have a conversation together in French than in Russian. However, we had the idea to use the notes taken during her courses to enhance my Russian vocabulary. She would show me what she did, and I would apply the notions and vocabulary she learned to Russian. It would produce a booklet with words in French, Russian, and even Uzbek, loosely based on the Guide parlé français-Uzbek-russe she found at home and gave me—a precious resource.

Another idea, quite conventional at first sight, would be to take note of everything in our environment, starting with home. From the apartment's front door, we would list every item from the floor to the ceiling and name them in French, Russian, and Uzbek (FRUZ). We would also list every item in the furniture, mostly a big wardrobe and cupboard, where we store Miya's food, among other tMiya's. We would then apply the same method to the other rooms.

In the hallway, for example, there is a doormat, a plate for Miya, a water fountain, a shoe rack, a wardrobe, a bench, a coffee table, two frames on the wall, and various commuturs. В коридоре, например, есть коврик, посуда для Мии, фонтанчик для воды для Мии, полка для обуви, шкаф, скамейка, журнальный столик, две рамки на стене, различные выключатели. Masalan, koridorda gilam, Miya uchun plastinka, Miya uchun suv favvorasi, poyabzal uchun javon, shkaf, skameyka, kofe stoli, devordagi ikkita ramka, turli xil kalitlar mavjud. Now that we have spent a few weeks each learning the other's message, we feel a bit more confident. Mind you, this statement in front of you this morning may act as a motivating element to implement what I have just described.

For this reason, and also because I was in another life a journalist, and I am now working in Toshkent in higher education, I would like to thank the Ministry of Higher Education, Sciences and Innovation of the Republic of Uzbekistan, as well as the

Journalism and Mass Communications the University of Uzbekistan, for letting me today share a small quantity of my experience in your country, a country for which, as for my wife, my love is growing every day. Sizga katta rahmat!

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BIRGALIKDA BIR-BIRINING TILINI O'RGANISH

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Annotatsiya. Ushbu tezisda muallif til o'rganish texnikasini hayotiy tajribalari orqali ifodalab bergan. Unda dunyo tillari – ingliz tili, ispan tili, fransuz tili hamda o'zbek tillarini o'rganish sabablari keltirilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: til o'rganish, ta'lim, maktab, metodika, talaba, o'quvchi